

Supporting information

BioCatHub: Acquisition of experimental data in biocatalysis based on the FAIR data principles.

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SI-1 Use cases

SI-1.1 Use case 1: Collection and creation of a new experiment

This example shows the documentation of the carboligation reaction of two pyruvates (including decarboxylation of one of the pyruvates) yielding acetolactate and carbon dioxide. The reaction is catalysed by the *Helicobacter canadensis* acetohydroxy acid synthase (HcAHAS) (not published). (Figure SI 1). The reaction is photometrically monitored by the decrease of pyruvate which is detected by absorption measurements at 333 nm.

Figure SI 1: Reaction of the *Helicobacter canadensis* acetohydroxyacid synthase (HcAHAS). The enzyme catalyses the carboligation of two pyruvate molecules yielding acetohydroxyacid and carbon dioxide.

On the landing page, a new experiment was started (Figure SI 2a). When starting a new experiment, the experimenter is guided through a five staged wizard like structure. The five stages are *vessels&volumes* (Figure SI 2b), *biocatalyst* (Figure SI 2c), *reactants*, *reaction conditions* and *experimental data* (Figure SI 2d). Metadata is defined as attributes described as combination of attribute category and value. The attribute category is a predefined keyword, like pH, temperature or concentration. The value is a variable which is connected to a specific attribute category. Each page contains a completeness check, which is visualized by a progress bar and turns green when complete.

A complete collection of attributes and primary data is named data set. Two additional features are to be named. When entering the enzyme name of *acetoxy acid* synthase to the *biocatalyst* search field (Figure SI 3a), Brenda DB is searched for a biocatalyst and the EC (enzyme commission) with this name. After selection of a specific enzyme, the EC number is forwarded in a follow up request to SabioRK and all available reactions are imported to BioCatHub connected to the EC number (Figure SI 3b). The imported reactions are then available in the *reactants* entry, there the requested reaction can be chosen from a dropdown menu (Figure SI 3b). If the reaction or the biocatalyst is not listed in Brenda-DB or SabioRK, the reaction can be designed individually by the experimenter. By this scheme, all available attributes categories are equipped with a value. As soon as all required fields are filled, the experimenter is guided to the experimental data page. Here, primary or measurement data is added in form of time dependent concentration data, which can be added either by a downloadable excel template or copy/paste (Figure SI 2d). Following, the measurement data is visualised by an xy-diagram. For the next and last step the overview page (Figure SI 2e) is opened. This page shows the reaction details in the five different segments. Furthermore, two different segments give the possibility to add personal information of the experimenter and additional general information of the reaction (Figure SI 2e). Following, data sets can be downloaded as EnzymeML document for local storage or uploaded to Zenodo for storage or publishing (Figure SI 2e).

a

BIOCATHUB

web application to create, collect and share experimental data in biocatalysis

REPORT EXPERIMENT

published experiments

name	reaction	location	volume	date
1000	1000-1000-1000	Wendisch, Austria	1000 mL	2020-10-10
1001	1001-1001-1001	Wendisch, Austria	1001 mL	2020-10-11
1002	1002-1002-1002	Wendisch, Austria	1002 mL	2020-10-12
1003	1003-1003-1003	Wendisch, Austria	1003 mL	2020-10-13
1004	1004-1004-1004	Wendisch, Austria	1004 mL	2020-10-14
1005	1005-1005-1005	Wendisch, Austria	1005 mL	2020-10-15
1006	1006-1006-1006	Wendisch, Austria	1006 mL	2020-10-16
1007	1007-1007-1007	Wendisch, Austria	1007 mL	2020-10-17
1008	1008-1008-1008	Wendisch, Austria	1008 mL	2020-10-18
1009	1009-1009-1009	Wendisch, Austria	1009 mL	2020-10-19
1010	1010-1010-1010	Wendisch, Austria	1010 mL	2020-10-20

b

BIOCATHUB

Overview

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reaction

reaction conditions

experimental data

type: microcentrifuge tube 1.5 mL

volume: 1

ADD ATTRIBUTE

c

BIOCATHUB

Overview

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reaction

reaction conditions

experimental data

name: E. coli

organism: E. coli

description: E. coli

ADD ATTRIBUTE

d

BIOCATHUB

Overview

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reaction

reaction conditions

experimental data

APPLIED CHECK FILE TO INPUT ENCOURAGEMENT ADD DATA FROM FILE (1x below)

ADD REAGENT & compound reference file

replicate 1

replicate 2

replicate 3

OD: 0.42

concentration: 100

level: 1

replicate 1

replicate 2

replicate 3

e

BIOCATHUB

experiment overview

experiment information

Name: Design 1000

Date: 2020-10-10

experimentist

Name: Heidegger

Location: Wendisch, Austria

Email: heidegger@biocathub.net

Phone: +43 35661

vessels & volumes

Name: microcentrifuge tube

Volume: 1 mL

reaction conditions

Temperature: 37 °C

pH: 7

Media: 100-100

experimental data

Reaction medium: Yersinia

Figure SI 2: Wizard like structure of BioCatHub. A: Shows the landing page of BioCatHub.net. Experimenters can upload EnzymeML documents, start new experiments or download already published experiments from zenodo. a-d: Show exemplary entries for collecting primary and metadata: b: (vessel&volumes), entry for collecting reaction vessel related metadata; c: (biocatalyst) entry for collecting enzyme related metadata; d: (experimental data), entry for collecting primary data. e (experiment) depicts an overview of the previously collected primary- and metadata.

a

BIOCATHUB

overview

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reactants

reaction conditions

experimental data

+ new experiment

× cancel experiment

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reactants

reaction conditions

experimental data

acetohydroxy

Acetohydroxy acid isomerase (5.4.99.3)

acetohydroxy acid isomeroreductase (1.1.1.86)

acetohydroxy acid reductoisomerase (1.1.1.86)

acetohydroxy acid synthase (2.2.1.6)

acetohydroxy acid synthase I (2.2.1.6)

acetohydroxy acid synthetase (2.2.1.6)

acetohydroxy-acid isomeroreductase (1.1.1.86)

acetohydroxy-acid reductoisomerase (1.1.1.86)

acetohydroxyacid dehydratase (4.2.1.9)

acetohydroxyacid isomeroreductase (1.1.1.86)

acetohydroxyacid synthase (2.2.1.6)

acetohydroxyacid synthase (4.1.1.1)

b

BIOCATHUB

overview

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reactants

reaction conditions

experimental data

+ new experiment

× cancel experiment

vessels & volumes

biocatalyst

reactants

reaction conditions

experimental data

acetolactate synthase

search reaction

manual reaction

select reaction

CO₂ + 2-Acetolactate = Pyruvate

CO₂ + (S)-2-Acetolactate = Pyruvate

Pyruvate + 2-Oxobuturate = CO₂ + (S)-2-Aceto-2-hydroxybutanoate

Pyruvate + Benzaldehyde = R-Phenylacetylcarbinol + CO₂

CC(=O)C(=O)O = CC(O)C(=O)O + O=C=O

	name	concentration	reaction role	formula
>	2 pyruvate		substrate	
>	2-acetolactate		product	
>	CO ₂		product	

< biocatalyst

overview

reaction conditions >

Figure SI 3: Example of requests from Brenda and SabioRK. BioCatHub offers the possibility to query BrendaDB and SabioRK. a: shows the biocatalyst entry. Experimenters can search for biocatalyst names, which are connected to EC numbers in BrendaDB. After the selection of one enzyme, the EC number is forwarded to SabioRK and the results available in SabioRK are displayed in the reactants entry (b).

SI-1.2 Use case 2: Customize experiment based on already existing EnzymeML documents

A common practise in biocatalysis is to measure an experimental setup multiple times and change one reaction attribute like temperature, pH, or the concentration of an individual reaction compount for each measurement. This helps to identify the influence of particular reaction parameters on the performance and characterise a catalyst or optimise a reaction setup . Therefore, BioCatHub offers the possibility to re-import already collected data sets. In this example, the data set from use case 1 is

reimported as EnzymeML to add further primary data measured at a pH value of 6 instead of 6.5 and the *overview* page is opened (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**e). In the *overview* page, the data set from use case 1 is displayed the attributes which have been altered in the experimental setup can be chosen. In this case, the *conditions* page is opened and the pH adjusted. Subsequently, the new primary data was attached, therefore the *experimental data* page is opened and the previous set of primary data is replaced. Subsequently, the experimenter selects the overview again and stores the collected data in form of an EnzymeML document locally or in a Zenodo repository, receiving a DOI. By this handling, experiments with small parameter changes can be deposited very conveniently with only some clicks, speeding-up data management under F.A.I.R. principles immensely.

SI-1.3 Use case 3: Addition of attributes for customisation purposes

Experimental procedures in biocatalysis are constantly changing and evolving as new knowledge on reaction setup, influence and optimal conditions is gained. BioCatHub provides the basic input fields, which are selected based on the STRENDA recommendations. This does of course not cover all experimental procedures. To enable the collection of further, not predefined metadata, BioCatHub provides the possibility to add additional attributes to every page. In this example, the experiment from use case 1 was repeated, but the influence of oxygen was determined. Therefore, the experiment was repeated under argon atmosphere. To add this information, the experimental set from use case 1 is re-imported as shown in Figure SI 4. From the overview page, the conditions page was opened Figure SI 4. Here additional attributes can be defined. Following, a new set of primary data was added and the reaction set was saved as EnzymeML locally.

a

b

Figure S1 4: Addition of further attributes to the reaction description. In this example an already existing EnzymeML document was uploaded and (a) and metadata concerning the gas phase was added to the reaction conditions entry by adding an attribute (b).

The overall purpose of BioCatHub is to enable an easy solution for in particular experimenters in biocatalysis to collect data sustainably according to the FAIR data principles. To realise this, it is necessary to be up to data with the STRENDa recommendations, enable the communication with public databases and permanently improve the usability for experimenters. One of the advantages BioCatHub provides is, that it uses tools and standards, like EnzymeML, the STRENDa recommendation or Zenodo and does not replace any already existing tool or infrastructure. Thereby experimenters and modellers will not have to get used to new file formats or processes but can use the collected data directly in already established processes. Furthermore, the collection of primary non processed data allows the re-analysis and thereby enhances the comparability with other experimental data.